

Challenges in Japan's Volunteer Probation Officer System: Trends and Future Directions

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Abstract

This study examines challenges facing Japan's volunteer probation officer (VPO) system, with particular focus on declining numbers of active VPOs. The number of active VPOs peaked at 49,389 in 2004 but has since declined to 46,358 by 2021, while average age rose from 60.1 to 65.0 years. Through analysis of previous research and participant observation, this paper explores relationships among VPOs, professional probation officers, and collaborative organizations such as BBS associations. The findings suggest that optimizing existing social resources and strengthening horizontal cooperation networks may be as crucial as increasing VPO numbers in addressing current challenges.

Keywords: volunteer probation officer, probation supervision, rehabilitation protection, collaborative organizations, BBS association

1. Introduction

This study focuses on challenges in Japan's volunteer probation officer system, particularly issues related to declining numbers of active officers. The volunteer probation officer (hereafter VPO) is a unique feature of Japan's rehabilitation protection system, serving as unpaid community volunteers who work alongside professional probation officers.

The number of active VPOs was 46,228 in 1975, peaked at 49,389 in 2004, then declined to 46,358 by 2021. Average age rose continuously from 60.1 years in 1975 to 65.0 years in 2021. Female representation increased from 17.9% in 1975 to 26.6% in 2021. These trends indicate a declining, aging VPO population with increasing female participation. Although statutory capacity is set at 52,500 nationwide under Article 2 of the Act on Volunteer Probation Officers of Japan (hereafter VPO Act), actual numbers consistently fall short, with the gap widening in recent years.

Reviewing prior studies conducted during the peak period of VPO numbers, Sugiyama (2002) identified several issues, emphasizing the urgent need to recruit qualified candidates, especially younger VPOs. Since average age had risen approximately 10 years from 53.2 in 1953 to 63.3 in 2002, he feared that aging would reduce activity levels and create generational gaps with supervisees, undermining VPO effectiveness. Oshikiri (2004) noted demographic changes, observing that approximately 70% of VPOs aged 60 and over would soon reach retirement. These concerns anticipated by Sugiyama (2002) and Oshikiri (2004) have materialized.

Approximately ten years later, Tanaka (2013) examined VPO recruitment, attributing declining numbers to the retirement system. Kobayashi (2013) cited difficulty finding candidates to fill vacancies, identifying weakened community relationships as a contributing factor. More recently, Tada (2021) explained that aging and unpaid status (Article 11 of the VPO Act) limit the candidate pool. He suggested that addressing this requires considering equitable treatment between VPOs and professional probation officers, citing the principle of "equal pay for equal work." Furthermore, he proposed expanding the rehabilitation supporter role to address functional limitations and burdens on VPOs.

Reviewing studies from 2000 to 2020 reveals recurring themes: shortage of qualified VPOs and underdeveloped collaborative organizations. Section 2 organizes basic information on VPO quotas while examining the essential question of VPO roles and appropriate staffing levels. Section 2-1 outlines procedures from case acceptance to completion. Section 2-2 addresses practical aspects of guidance during interviews, touching on roles of collaborators and collaborative organizations. Section 2-3 examines declining VPO numbers through population dynamics, confirming relative proportions from the eligible

population base rather than quotas alone. Section 3 summarizes observations from the author's practice regarding rehabilitation supporter potential as proposed by Tada (2021). Section 4 onward records personal views on future collaborative possibilities, building on considerations from Sections 2 and 3.

2. Background on the Volunteer Probation Officer System

2-1. Case Acceptance Procedures

Unless otherwise noted, this section references Ministry of Justice Rehabilitation Bureau (2018) and Editorial Committee for the 70-Year History of Rehabilitation Protection (2020), incorporating understanding from the author's participant observation.

VPOs belong to districts within protection areas in each prefecture and supervise persons residing within their assigned district. VPO activities consist of conducting interviews and responding based on results. VPOs work cooperatively with professional probation officers responsible for their district; supervision begins when the district's professional officer requests case acceptance. Cases are classified as Type 1 through Type 4 Supervision, or Living Environment Adjustment—a form of community-based support prior to or in lieu of formal probation supervision. VPOs decide whether to accept a case after hearing and understanding the explanations provided by professional officers. Without expressing acceptance after these explanations, one does not become responsible for supervision or environmental adjustment. Therefore, caseloads per VPO are not constant.

When professional officers request case acceptance, they provide advance notice before formal written notification. After meeting with the professional officer at the probation office, the supervisee contacts the VPO to arrange the initial interview. Interviews involve home visits and office visits; regardless of classification, VPOs make home visits initially. This allows confirming home environment including guardians, which is crucial for effective supervision. In this context, observing whether incidents stem from the supervisee's personality or environmental factors has meaning (Matsumoto & Saito, 2018). Since most VPOs lack medical or psychological professional training, they supervise while understanding family, friendships, and home environment, with an awareness of their shared human dignity (Shimoi et al., 2020).

Qualified VPOs are expected to be respected for integrity and conduct, have enthusiasm and time for duties, maintain stable livelihoods, and possess health and activity capacity. They are not necessarily expected to fulfill specialized professional roles. Finding qualified VPOs thus involves both traditional networking through local connections and creating mechanisms for broader community recruitment (Oyama & Koyama, 2022). With sequential establishment of Rehabilitation Protection Support Centers, mechanisms allowing interested citizens to inquire proactively could also be explored (Rehabilitation Protection Network, 2022).

Table 1. Number of Protection Districts by Prefecture

Prefecture	Districts	Prefecture	Districts	Prefecture	Districts	Prefecture	Districts
Hokkaido	67	Tokyo	33	Shiga	9	Kagawa	9
Aomori	11	Kanagawa	45	Kyoto	22	Ehime	12
Iwate	14	Niigata	21	Osaka	56	Kochi	15
Miyagi	17	Toyama	11	Hyogo	34	Fukuoka	30
Akita	12	Ishikawa	8	Nara	14	Saga	8
Yamagata	11	Fukui	10	Wakayama	10	Nagasaki	11
Fukushima	18	Yamanashi	13	Tottori	8	Kumamoto	16
Ibaraki	19	Nagano	19	Shimane	9	Oita	12
Tochigi	13	Gifu	21	Okayama	18	Miyazaki	12

Prefecture	Districts	Prefecture	Districts	Prefecture	Districts	Prefecture	Districts
Gunma	13	Shizuoka	28	Hiroshima	23	Kagoshima	15
Saitama	25	Aichi	42	Yamaguchi	13	Okinawa	8
Chiba	26	Mie	25	Tokushima	9		

Note: Based on Editorial Committee for the 70-Year History of Rehabilitation Protection (2020), pp. 531-553.

2-2. Interviewing Supervised Persons

This section references Sakamoto (2016) and Ministry of Justice Rehabilitation Bureau (2018), incorporating observations from the author's participant observation, focusing on social resource utilization considered when facing interview difficulties—relevant to examining rehabilitation supporter potential indicated by Tada (2021).

VPOs have access to VPO associations and probation offices. Associations have colleagues active in the community; probation offices have professional officers serving as supervisors. When facing difficult interview situations, places and opportunities for consultation exist (Administrative Evaluation Bureau, 2021). The former comprises those with local knowledge; the latter, those advancing treatment from professional expertise. Regarding interview content, VPOs submit regular reports to probation offices, enabling continuous monitoring of supervisee situations. When psychological states or family relationships change during interviews, telephone consultation with professional officers provides the quickest resolution for issues beyond VPO capacity. Nevertheless, since VPOs understand certain guidance methods, they remain mindful of incorporating essential topics into conversations with supervisees (Table 2).

VPO interviews emphasize a natural, non-technical approach, so counseling techniques like psychological professionals use are not required. However, for VPOs dealing with diverse supervisees, updated interviewing approaches will continue being sought despite maintaining naturalness. One learning tool supporting such efforts is the monthly magazine "Rehabilitation Protection" produced by the Japan Rehabilitation Aid Association, delivered monthly to VPOs. Edited thematically each month, it serves as a valuable case-specific information source.

When human support is necessary, examples include designating multiple VPOs, requesting cooperation from BBS associations and cooperative employers, and maintaining mutually beneficial regional networks. How to strengthen such horizontal collaborative connections may depend on Information and Communication Technology (ICT) adoption (Morimoto, 2022).

In addition, online lectures from the Japan Rehabilitation Aid Association have become more utilized recently through live streaming and recorded videos, making expert knowledge accessible. For VPOs in areas without local experts, online information sharing is particularly valuable. Since some supervisees struggle with multiple relationships, supporting skill development for trusted VPOs makes sense by creating unified contact points. This is particularly important because rapport formation is indispensable between VPOs and supervisees (Oyama, Hatano, & Hashimoto, 2021).

Table 2. Overview of Guidance Topics in Interviews

Topic	Overview
Family Relationships	For supervisees to reform and rehabilitate, not only securing food, clothing, and shelter but also having close supporters for rehabilitation motivation is extremely important.
Employment/Education	Continuing work or studies produces favorable effects including economic stability and improved friendships, leading to

Topic	Overview
	self-confidence and future hope. Confirming such situations in interviews connects to supervisees' sense of self-affirmation.
Friendships	Relationships with friends uninvolved in crime or delinquency promote rehabilitation and lifestyle improvement. Consultation partners during difficulties provide emotional support and serve as life models.
Living Situation	Poverty and life difficulties increase crime possibilities like theft. Knowing from living conditions whether basic needs are secured and whether self-abandonment from difficulties has occurred is valuable.
Alcohol and Drugs	Repeatedly drinking excessively or using drugs to relieve stress can lead to dependency, making stopping difficult. Recovery requires not only the supervisee's will to stop but also surrounding support.
Leisure Activities	Healthy leisure activities enable appropriate stress release when unpleasant situations occur, sometimes preventing crime.

Note: Based on Ministry of Justice Rehabilitation Bureau (2018), pp. 98-101.

2-3. Active VPO Numbers

The VPO Act stipulates nationwide capacity not exceeding 52,500, with quotas per protection district determined considering "area population," "economy," "crime situation," and "other circumstances." While quotas are determined considering these factors, we reconsider the relationship between VPO numbers and quotas while examining population dynamics.

In 2004, the number of active VPOs nationwide was 49,389, while Japanese population aged 20-75 was approximately 92,009 thousand. Focusing only on age and taking the eligible demographic as the base, the ratio actually serving as VPOs was 0.537 per thousand. Examining ratios chronologically from 2004-2015 shows minimum 0.531 per thousand in 2006 and maximum 0.541 per thousand in 2009, with ratios from 2013-2015 above the 12-year average of 0.537 per thousand (Table 3). When tracking VPO numbers over years while considering age-eligible population, comprehensive population observation suggests VPO numbers maintain relative equilibrium.

Table 3. Ratios of Japanese Population to Active VPOs (per thousand)

Year	Active VPOs	Japanese Population (20-75)	‰	Total Population	‰
2004	49,389	92,009,000	0.537	93,259,000	0.530
2005	48,917	91,805,000	0.533	93,111,000	0.525
2006	48,688	91,608,000	0.531	92,954,000	0.524
2007	48,564	91,325,000	0.532	92,737,000	0.524
2008	48,919	90,941,000	0.538	92,405,000	0.529
2009	48,936	90,537,000	0.541	91,961,000	0.532
2010	48,851	90,831,000	0.538	92,251,000	0.530
2011	48,664	90,310,000	0.539	91,681,000	0.531
2012	48,221	89,772,000	0.537	91,083,000	0.529
2013	47,990	89,235,000	0.538	90,576,000	0.530
2014	47,914	88,770,000	0.540	90,146,000	0.532

Year	Active VPOs	Japanese Population (20-75)	‰	Total Population	‰
2015	47,872	88,678,000	0.540	90,169,000	0.531

Note: The difference between total and Japanese population represents foreign population.

This paper uses Japanese population because commissioning foreigners as VPOs was once abandoned. Calculating with either population shows little difference. Ratios use active VPO numbers as numerator and Japanese population as denominator, displayed in per thousand.

Source: Japanese population from e-Stat long-term time series data "Population by Age, Sex (Total Population, Japanese Population 2000-2020 as of October 1)"; active VPO numbers from Ministry of Justice website Rehabilitation Protection "Probation Officer System in Numbers."

An important issue here is understanding what challenges are embedded regarding supervision efforts based solely on VPO number changes. We need to know whether decreasing VPOs leads to increased caseloads and burdens, or whether cooperative systems including professional officers prevent burden increases—which reflects reality. Kitazawa (2003) notes in "Transformation of Collaborative System Theory Between Professional Officers and VPOs" that probation supervision formed based on given organizational resources, suggesting attention to how collaborative organizations historically functioned interactively. He argues that considering organizational "self-awareness" alongside individual practitioners' "self-awareness" in treatment processes, while thinking about VPO shortages, leads to seeking solutions emphasizing mutual cooperation.

While probation offices are undoubtedly VPOs' main collaborative organization, understanding cooperation among cooperative employers, BBS associations, rehabilitation protection women's associations, and others matters for considering future VPO engagement prospects. At the same time, attention is needed regarding whether professional officers will approach supervisees while venturing into judicial welfare domains with social work perspectives. Regarding supervisee approaches, Nakamura (2019) explains that some professional officers conduct treatment while consciously building VPO cooperation as social work technicians and constructing relationships with collaborative community resource organizations. Regarding rehabilitation supporter potential proposed by Tada (2021), mapping connection mechanisms among collaborative organizations, connection frequency, and hierarchical approach methods is necessary. Furthermore, investigating how collaborative supervisee support based on self-awareness among those in collaborative organizations impacts VPO shortages is needed (Ueda, 2012). However, analyzing such approaches will continue in separate future considerations.

3. Relationships Among Professional Officers, VPOs, and Collaborative Organizations

On January 25, 2013, a three-party meeting among the National Federation of VPO Associations Chairman, Japan BBS Federation President, and Japan Federation of Women's Associations for Rehabilitation Protection President confirmed advancing cooperation and collaboration with collaborative organizations for community rehabilitation protection effectiveness. Understanding that community rehabilitation protection involves rehabilitation protection facilities and cooperative employers reveals various supervisee approaches from different positions and roles (Japan Society for Rehabilitation Protection Studies, 2021).

At probation offices, supervisors and deputies engage in district supervision cooperating with VPOs while conducting liaison and coordination with collaborative organizations like

BBS associations and rehabilitation protection women's associations (Table 4). Some professional officers serve as social rehabilitation coordination officers assigned to probation offices, engaging in supervisee social rehabilitation from mental health and welfare perspectives (Kakiuchi, 2020). From their respective positions and roles, collaborative organizations exist around VPOs working cooperatively. Supervisee social rehabilitation efforts can thus be regarded as socially implemented. If VPO interviews requiring advanced techniques and specialized knowledge can seek collaborative cooperation, VPO anxieties reduce, potentially increasing new VPO candidates. However, VPO difficulties seem to depend more on supervisee attitudes and interview motivation than on such techniques and knowledge (Kubo & Yakiyama, 2011). Despite the arrangement of peaceful interview settings at promised times and locations, supervisees who struggle with punctuality often fail to appear at interview times. Excuses and lies like "I forgot" or "I never promised" occur. When supervisee families are uncooperative, VPOs become manipulated by supervisees and families, with problem behaviors imposing burdens on VPOs. Beyond caseload numbers, supervisee and family attitudes significantly impact VPOs, with fundamental problems existing beyond VPO numbers and collaborative organization frameworks. Improving supervisees' basic interpersonal communication skills requires understanding through homes and familiar living environments, not probation offices or VPOs. However, particularly for supervisees falling into delinquency, various environmental difficulties exist in backgrounds including family relationships (Shimoi et al., 2020). Furthermore, making rehabilitation protection programs effective for supervisees faces noted limitations in opportunities gaining delinquency awareness (Hiroi, 2020). From this perspective, if approaching the juvenile delinquent age group, while limited to juvenile supervisees, BBS association cooperation allows supervisees gaining delinquency awareness from same-generation normative behavior.

The BBS (Big Brothers and Sisters) Association is an organization conducting volunteer activities as good friends in positions like "older brothers" and "older sisters," staying close to boys and girls with various challenges including delinquency. The Kyoto Youth Protection Student League established in 1947 marks the beginning of Japan's BBS movement, reportedly started when young people pained by many juvenile delinquents' unfortunate appearances in postwar chaos considered what they could do (Japan BBS Federation, 2019). Among methods staying close to boys and girls, one "friend activity" BBS members practice cooperating with VPOs is "academic support." Since entering high school or passing high school equivalency examinations opens supervisee future prospects and triggers rehabilitation, university students and others providing academic support represents meaningful rehabilitation protection initiatives.

In addition, since the Probation Office Organization Regulations stipulate private activity support specialist roles, including liaison and coordination with rehabilitation protection organizations like BBS associations, VPO cooperation is expected to function increasingly (Table 4). A recent BBS association characteristic shows increasing student member ratios to all members (Table 5). Conducting awareness activities for students interested in rehabilitation protection at universities and providing volunteer opportunity information connects to strengthening VPO cooperative relationships while potentially securing VPO candidates.

Table 4. Fukuoka Probation Office Professional Officer Assignment Table (Other Duties)

Other Duties	Main Office	Main Deputy	Iizuka	Kitakyushu	Kitakyushu Deputy
Recidivism Prevention Promotion	●			●	
Entrance Support/Pre-adjustment	●			●	●

Other Duties	Main Office	Main Deputy	Iizuka	Kitakyushu	Kitakyushu Deputy
CFP	•			•	
Pardon Affairs Management	•			•	
Case Management	•	•		•	•
Biker Gang Countermeasures	•	•		•	•
Rehabilitation Guidance	•	•		•	•
General Traffic Instruction	•	•		•	•
Short-term Traffic Supervision	•	•	•	•	
Pre-release Education	•	•			•
Social Contribution Activities	•	•	•	•	
Social Participation Activities	•		•		
Violent Organizations	•			•	
Drug Treatment	•		•	•	
Special Treatment	•			•	
Guardian Associations	•			•	
Employment Support	•			•	•
BBS Associations	•			•	•
Rehabilitation Protection Women's Associations	•			•	•
Community Awareness Campaign	•			•	•
Special Coordination	•			•	•
Independent Living Homes	•			•	•
Training	•			•	•
Victim Services	•				

Note: Based on Fukuoka Prefecture Rehabilitation Protection Association "Fukuoka Rehabilitation Protection" No. 854, p. 7 (as of April 1, 2022). "Main office" refers to Fukuoka Probation Office in Fukuoka City. • indicates assigned personnel or unit teams.

Table 5. Trends in BBS Member Numbers, District Associations, Friend Activities, and Student Members

Year	Districts	Total Members	Friend Activities	Student Members	Student %
1978	540	7,741	932	685	9
1981	486	7,220	709	571	8
1982	501	7,284	705	595	8
1983	503	7,435	726	641	9
1984	494	7,055	677	634	9
1985	547	6,872	541	562	8
1988	565	6,789	459	530	8
1989	564	6,756	431	637	9
1990	557	6,542	427	630	10
1991	574	6,383	379	618	10
1992	569	6,458	305	760	12
1993	567	6,129	237	716	12

Year	Districts	Total Members	Friend Activities	Student Members	Student %
1994	566	6,219	281	864	14
1995	561	6,230	277	1,004	16
1998	585	6,123	296	1,270	21
1999	578	6,225	321	1,361	22
2000	582	6,047	272	1,355	22
2001	591	6,053	300	1,529	25
2002	581	6,100	267	1,565	26
2003	591	6,169	308	1,835	30
2004	571	6,024	296	1,894	31
2005	564	5,699	269	1,831	32
2007	535	4,543	279	1,429	31
2008	521	4,307	233	1,404	33
2009	495	4,217	206	1,431	34
2010	489	4,469	268	1,685	38
2011	487	4,666	361	1,851	40
2012	469	4,606	389	1,935	42
2013	481	4,740	227	2,094	44
2014	479	4,514	273	1,918	42
2015	478	4,512	216	1,804	40
2016	477	4,738	277	2,165	46
2017	472	4,509	176	2,015	45
2018	464	4,459	172	1,939	43

Note: Based on Japan BBS Federation (2019) "BBS Movement 70th Anniversary Commemorative Publication," p. 231. Blank cells represent missing information in original source.

4. Challenges

Probation supervision involves guidance and support by professional officers and VPOs enabling persons who committed crimes or juveniles with delinquency to rehabilitate within society. As treatment occurs within society, standard procedures from supervision start to completion are established. Without compliance violations, measures like supervision release or period completion occur. Information is shared between professional officers and VPOs, with common goals that supervision ends without adverse measures. However, examining relationships with other collaborative organizations beyond professional officers and VPOs reveals no specific shared goals.

BBS friend activity request forms issued by probation offices under supervisor names provide supervisee information limited to general details like "delinquency type," "family structure," "contact information," and "activity request content." BBS associations cooperating with responsible VPOs can support supervisee future prospects through friend activities. The problem is that even when VPOs seek various support, access methods—how to connect with social resources like BBS associations—often remain poorly understood. In summary, while securing qualified VPOs is urgent, thinking about optimizing existing social resources could contribute to situation improvement from angles separate from VPO numbers.

Particularly, academic BBS associations within universities also position universities themselves promoting community-rooted activities, with volunteer activities in actual society

becoming opportunities for students connecting with society. VPO associations and probation offices dispatching personnel to intermediate places like community activities could enable exchanges connecting to mutually beneficial cooperation. The question, then, is how such contact points can be newly identified; one personal view is presented below. As an intermediate place, attention can focus on housing support trends as rehabilitation protection measures (Seto, 2021). Among these, independent preparation homes based on "Emergency Housing Security and Independence Support Measures" started in fiscal 2011 have increased to 447 registered businesses as of April 1, 2021. Independent preparation homes are registered with probation offices and, for cases requiring supervisee protection, entrust "accommodation," "meal provision," and daily life guidance to operating organizations like NPOs. According to Seto (2021), housing support organization cooperation has expanded support for persons requiring consideration who have social life difficulties, with probation supervision subjects also becoming persons requiring consideration under the revised Housing Safety Net Act. Such connections with various organizations and backing support measures according to legal revisions can be expected to connect to VPO network construction. The extent to which local governments, related organizations, and VPO capacity for actively adopting such new attempts permeates may become future challenges.

5. Conclusion

VPO activity challenges have been identified in several previous studies as difficulty securing qualified VPOs. As factors contributing to continued active VPO number decline, besides absent willing candidates, retirement system implementation has begun impacting. While declining active numbers would increase VPO caseloads, examining probation supervision rate trends like numbers entering supervision reveals supervisee numbers themselves declining (Table 6). This does not mean declining supervisee numbers make VPO number decreases acceptable; verifying VPO decline challenges remains necessary. However, since professional officer-VPO relationships are maintained closely, prioritizing and clarifying challenges while considering achieving more effective supervision through these relationships seems more realistic.

For professional officers, an assessment tool called CFP (Case Formulation in Probation/Parole) introduced from January 2021 moves toward producing more appropriate treatment policies through scientific and systematic assessment rather than individual professional officer experience and capacity influencing decisions (Hada & Katsuta, 2021). CFP grasps crime and delinquency connection factors from interviews and various information, also grasps rehabilitation and improvement strengths, reflecting in supervision implementation plans and contributing to information sharing with VPOs. Particularly as treatment density by professional officers and VPOs becomes more visible, "interview frequency," "home visits or office visits," and other "supervision implementation plan" aspects can be valued by VPOs.

Regarding relationships with other collaborative organizations, rather than viewing them as VPO support organizations, horizontal mutual helping relationships should be constructed. For supervisees, social rehabilitation is not realized only through supervision; living and working places are indispensable for independent living. Even when supervisees are uncooperative with supervision, cooperative employers and independent preparation home operators can also encourage supervisees receiving supervision. Instead of professional officers and VPOs working in isolation, collaboration with collaborative organizations already closer to supervisee daily lives connects to recidivism prevention, with cooperation with existing volunteer organizations like BBS associations indispensable for supervisee rehabilitation support. For recidivism prevention, professional counseling and self-help group meetings are also effective, with collaborative work with professionals and self-help groups for returning to society expected to have larger effects (Kakegawa et al., 2018).

As a future challenge, making relationships among these collaborative organizations as close as possible while understanding mutual position and thinking differences matters. To that end, bold methods like commissioning VPOs on limited terms from other collaborative organizations, volunteer organizations, and professional organizations as personnel exchange should be considered. Also, since "Rehabilitation Protection System" exists as designated subjects for acquiring social worker and psychiatric social worker qualifications, designating probation offices during training institution practical training periods could increase personnel exchange and deepen related organization understanding. Understanding institutional and other barriers exist and things will not proceed smoothly, organically connecting social resources is considered to lead to improving performance of various organizations and personnel including VPOs.

Table 6. Numbers Entering Probation Supervision

Year	Total	Year	Total	Year	Total
1990	97,801	2000	75,995	2010	47,562
1991	93,218	2001	75,114	2011	45,199
1992	90,419	2002	75,197	2012	44,056
1993	82,052	2003	70,949	2013	42,117
1994	75,276	2004	68,194	2014	39,995
1995	71,851	2005	62,562	2015	38,103
1996	72,177	2006	58,841	2016	35,341
1997	76,078	2007	54,878	2017	32,538
1998	77,266	2008	50,717	2018	30,845
1999	77,535	2009	48,488	2019	29,183

Note: Based on 2020 White Paper on Crime Part 2/Chapter 5/Section 3/1 "Probation Supervision Subject Numbers," extracting approximately 30 years from 1990-2019.

Notes

1. Based on Ministry of Justice Rehabilitation Bureau materials (Crime White Paper website, accessed August 29, 2022), data from 2021 "White Paper on Crime" Part 2/Chapter 5/Section 6.
2. Subjects and periods of probation supervision: persons placed under supervision by family court decision (Type 1)—until age 20 (or 2 years if less; for specified juveniles aged 18-19, 6 months or 2 years); persons paroled from juvenile training schools (Type 2)—parole period; persons granted parole (Type 3)—parole period; persons granted suspended sentence with supervision (Type 4)—suspended sentence period; persons paroled from women's guidance homes (Type 5)—parole period.
3. Profile changes refer to increases in unemployed persons (housewives and retirees), confirmation of female increases, and advancing aging.
4. While the retirement system began operation from April 2004, concerns about widening generational gaps with juveniles and worries about declining capacity with age were noted. Regarding new VPO candidate ages, the Ministry of Justice in commission notifications established in principle an age limit of 66 years or younger.
5. Indicated as personnel who can demonstrate certain expertise and have abilities demonstrating strength toward rehabilitation protection activities, with preference for personnel recommended by community-related organizations.
6. The author's involvement in rehabilitation protection activities is limited to VPO

- associations, BBS associations, and independence promotion centers, but conducts participant observation under members operating according to formalized norms of probation offices and BBS federations.
7. The author is a VPO belonging to professional officers within Kitakyushu Branch of Fukuoka Probation Office (Yahata Protection District: Yahata East Ward and Yahata West Ward of Kitakyushu City), responsible for supervisees (probation supervision or living environment adjustment) with residences in the district.
 8. Since Type 5 currently exists only at Tokyo Women's Guidance Home, to the best of the author's knowledge, cases of VPOs handling such supervision are unknown.
 9. Investigates post-release housing environments for persons detained in correctional facilities and coordinates living environments favorable for rehabilitation.
 10. Related documents including "Supervision Assignment Notification," "Case Investigation Form," "Supervision Implementation Plan," compliance matter notification, and life action guideline notification are also sent.
 11. References Article 3 of the Act on Volunteer Probation Officers of Japan.
 12. Supervisor refers to professional officers assigned to each district area.
 13. For professional officer recruitment examinations, besides National Public Service General and Regular Service Examinations, there is the Ministry of Justice Specialist Staff (Human Sciences) Employment Examination (Probation Supervision Division), with recruitment format premised on requiring high insight regarding people and society.
 14. Accessing Japan Rehabilitation Aid Association website allows confirmation of online lecture information and recorded teaching material information (accessed October 13, 2022).
 15. References Article 2 of the Act on Volunteer Probation Officers of Japan.
 16. While upper age limits for VPOs are established, only about ten active officers in their 20s exist nationwide. Therefore, the age demographic used here is from 20-75 years.
 17. References Yomiuri Shimbun July 6, 2007 edition regarding appointment challenges of Japanese-Brazilian VPO candidates.
 18. Three-party declaration on rehabilitation protection volunteer collaboration can be confirmed at Japan Rehabilitation Aid Association website (accessed October 27, 2022).
 19. Besides organizations addressed in this paper, collaborative organizations include organizations supporting separation from addiction such as MAC, DARIC, and AA, with probation offices serving as intermediaries.
 20. The Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology has established guidelines enabling universities, local governments, and industry to cooperate in each region for community-rooted activities.
 21. As of March 31, 2011, there were 166 registered independent preparation home businesses; as of April 1, 2021, there were 447 registered businesses.
 22. Kagoshima Prefecture Housing Support Council website provides detailed housing support mechanisms (accessed December 5, 2022).
 23. Social rehabilitation coordination officers work at probation offices engaging in living environment investigation, living environment adjustment, and mental health observation based on specialized knowledge regarding mental health and welfare.

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